

EVALUATION OF THE STATIC AND DYNAMIC PERFORMANCE OF ALUMINIUM AND COMPOSITE JOINTS FOR RAIL VEHICLE APPLICATIONS

U. Galappaththi¹, M. Johnson² and G. Assinder³

¹Department of Mechanical, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering
University of Nottingham C-08, ITRC Building, University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD
Email: udayanga.galappaththi @nottingham.ac.uk

²Department of Mechanical, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering
University of Nottingham, Coates B79, University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD
Email: michael.johnson @nottingham.ac.uk

³Department of Mechanical, Materials and Manufacturing Engineering
University of Nottingham, Coates B79, University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD
Email: eayga@nottingham.ac.uk

Keywords: Composite Joining, Frictional Grip Joints, Rail Applications

ABSTRACT

The modular construction principle allows greater flexibility for integrating composite structural components onto a rail car body. Limited knowledge in the area of composite joining technologies acts as a barrier for using modular construction principles for the rail applications. Aluminium frictional grip joints frequently are used for assembling side-walls, floors and roofs of the rail car body structure. The main objective of the current testing programme is to evaluate the static and dynamic performance of aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joints. The existing aluminium frictional grip joint was tested and the bench marks were set as a 36.7kN slip load and a 66.5kN ultimate failure load. The aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joint was designed to achieve the same reference values and the experimental evidence has shown that a slip load of 32.2kN and ultimate failure load of 68.2kN could be achieved by using novel big head inserts. Two specimens were tested under dynamic loading (6kN, R=1) and also showed good fatigue performance and residual strength when compared to the existing aluminium frictional grip joint.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent studies have shown that light weighting is an important area of concern with regard to the rail industry, particularly for reducing the track damage costs [1]. The strength to weight ratio of composite materials is lower compared to aluminum and steel [2] and they were considered as a possible alternative for those metals. Composites currently are used in the rail industry mainly to produce semi-structural interior components, which primarily includes ceilings, window panels, partition walls, gangway panels, door pillars, cabinet panels, seats, inter-circulation panels, under-seat boxes, inter-deck floors and catering units [3].

Since the late 1970's, numerous programs have been carried out to investigate the application of composite materials for producing exterior rail car body structures [4] [5]. Each of these projects had their objectives, specific methodology and useful recommendations. Analysis of the outcome of most of these projects suggests that the common challenges were meeting the existing fire-safety regulations without compromising the mechanical performance (impact and fatigue) and the higher cost associated with composite manufacture. The secondary challenge is the specification of how the composite components will be joined to the main aluminium/steel structure. A number of composite joining methods are available. Most commonly, these include mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding

techniques. Each of these methods has their own advantages and limitations. Frictional grip joints are used widely in the design of rail structures or mechanisms. In these joints, the shear forces at its interface, are transferred by friction of the clamping bolts, and not by the bearing or shearing of the bolts themselves. Figure 1 illustrates a typical side wall/floor Huck Lockbolted connection being assembled of a rail car body vehicle structure [6].

Figure 1: Frictional grip joint (Huck Lockbolted Joint) applications in the rail industry [6]

In this context, an experimental study which aims to evaluate the performance of the aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joint is extremely important. This paper illustrates the design process used for developing this type of frictional grip joint.

2 LOAD TRANSFER MECHANISM FOR FRICTIONAL GRIP JOINTS

Frictional grip joints are produced by pressing two plates together such that a clamping pressure develops between the plates. This phenomenon resists the relative movement/slip between the plates and the tensile force is transferred from one plate to the other plate by the induced friction. Figure 2 illustrates the loading configurations on an ordinary joint and a frictional grip joint.

Figure 2: Ordinary bolted joint configurations versus a frictional grip joint

The most important design consideration for the frictional grip joint is that under the service load the tensile force on the plates does not exceed the frictional resistance, preventing relative slip between the two plates. If the frictional resistance between the two plates is exceeded, then the joint reverts to the load condition on an ordinary bolt.

3 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The first step of the experimental programme was to establish a bench mark for developing a novel aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joint. The existing aluminium-aluminium Huck Lockbolted joint was tested under tensile loading with slip and the ultimate failure loads being measured. These values were set as bench marks for the new design. The testing results were used for evaluating how the fastener interacts with the joining material and the failure modes of the joints were carefully observed. After establishing a bench mark, an aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joint was tested using the same conditions. It was observed that the aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joint began to fail in bearing. As a result, a “big head” insert was used to reduce the bearing damage. The new aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joint with the big head insert was evaluated for both static and dynamic performance.

3.1 Test Specimens

The aluminium-aluminium made Huck Lockbolted specimens were manufactured from thick aluminium sheet sections, grade 6005A; condition T6 with the grain direction parallel to the specimen width. Two plates, 140mm length, 65mm width and 6mm thick were used to produce the joint. The fasteners were Huck Lockbolts with flanged heads and collars (Figure 3).

Figure 3: The specimen side view with dimensions

The aluminium-carbon fibre composite frictional grip joints were manufactured from two plates (140mm × 65mm × 6mm). One plate was made from the same material which was used for producing aluminium-aluminium specimens and the other plate was manufactured from Cytec’s MTM 58FRB carbon/epoxy prepreg (12k woven fabric) and an autoclave process. Each ply has a thickness of 0.4mm and the stacking sequence was [0, 90, 45,-45]_s. The inserts were bonded into a 19 mm diameter hole in the composite plate. The fasteners were Huck Lockbolts, with flanged heads and collars. Figure 4 illustrates the three types of specimens, which were used for the testing programme

Figure 4: Three type of specimen used for the testing programme

Figure 5 illustrates the dimensions of the big head insert which was used for reducing early bearing damage of the composite specimens.

Figure 5: Configurations of the big head insert

3.2 Test Method

A single column Zwick Roell (Zmart.Pro) machine was used to undertake the tensile testing programme, which had a load capacity of 200kN (Figure 6- left view). An electro-microscope was positioned close to the specimen, with the live feed output used to identify the slip load for each specimen. The slip load was evaluated by identifying the exact time elapsed prior to the onset of slip by viewing the microscopic video images and then identifying the force applied on the specimen from the machine clock time. The tensile testing machine and video capturing was started at the same time to facilitate this process.

The Instron servo-hydraulic testing machine was used for fatigue testing. Two specimens were tested at R=0.1, 7Hz frequency and under a 6kN tensile loading. The available fatigue testing data showed that the aluminium Huck Lockbolted bolted joint was able to run only to an average of 4.2×10^6 cycles under the fatigue loading before failure. Therefore, the residual strength of the aluminium-composite joints was evaluated after testing 3.6×10^6 and 6.6×10^6 fatigue cycles.

Figure 6: Tensile testing (left) and fatigue testing fixtures (right)

4 TEST RESULTS

4.1 Aluminum-aluminium Huck Lockbolted joints

Slip Load

Analysis of the video images suggests that the slipping starts around 36.7 kN. The rate of slipping increased after 38.1kN. A study of the video images for the Huck Lockbolted joints indicated a similar slip load for all three specimens (Figure 7)

Figure 7: Comparison of slip and ultimate failure loads for aluminium- joint

Ultimate Failure Load

The ultimate failure loads are similar for each of the specimen with the average ultimate failure load being 66.5kN (Figure 7).

Mode of Failure

Analysis of the modes of failure of the tested specimens suggests that the failure is initiated through bearing damage and then the final failure is from shear out or cleavage (Figure 7).

4.2 Aluminum-composite Huck Lockbolted joints without insert

Slip Load

Analysis of the video images suggests that slipping starts at approximately 29.5kN (Figure 8).

Ultimate Failure Load

The ultimate failure loads show similar values for each of the specimens with an average ultimate failure load of 64.1kN (Figure 8).

Mode of Failure

Analysis of the modes of failure of the tested specimens suggests that the failure is initiated through bearing damage and then the final failure is from shear out or cleavage (Figure 8). Visible bearing damage was observed at around 30kN.

Figure 8: Comparison of slip and ultimate failure loads for aluminium-composite joints without insert

4.3 Aluminum-composite Huck Lockbolted joints with big head insert

Slip Load

Analysis of the video images suggests that the slipping starts at approximately 32.2kN (Figure 9).

Ultimate Failure Load

The ultimate failure loads show similar values for each of the specimens with an average ultimate failure load of 68.2kN (Figure 9).

Mode of Failure

Analysis of the modes of failure of the tested specimens suggests that the onset of failure is through bearing damage and then the final failure is from shear out or cleavage (Figure 9). With the use of the big head insert, the bearing damage was reduced and visible bearing damage was not seen until 60kN. During the testing, the aluminum plate first started to bend about the bolt as is typical for a lap joint configuration.

Figure 9: Comparison of slip and ultimate failure loads for aluminium-composite joints with the big head insert

This bending generated a moment leading to the ultimate failure of the specimens (Figure 10).

Figure 10: The aluminium plate began to bend around the bolt axis before initiating bearing failure

4.4 Residual strength of aluminum-composite Huck Lockbolted joints with big head insert

Two specimens that were equivalent to those in Section 4.3 (aluminium-composite Huck Lockbolted with big head insert) were subjected to fatigue loading (6kN, R=0.1). Subsequently, these specimens were tested under tensile loading as described in Section 3.2. Table 1 illustrates the measured residual strength values.

Specimen	Maximum Fatigue Load Applied (kN)	No. Cycles	Slip Load (kN)	Ultimate Failure Load-Fatigued (kN)
NE-2	6	3.6×10^6	26.9	67.58
NE-4	6	6.6×10^6	24.1	64.94

The fatigue tested specimens showed a minimal reduction of 3% in the ultimate failure load (average = 66.3kN) as compared to non-fatigue loaded specimens (average = 68.2kN, see Section 4.3). The slip loads of the fatigue tested specimens were 26.9kN and 24.1kN. The slip load of the equivalent non-fatigued specimens (Section 4.3) was approximately 32.2kN. This represents a reduction of 20% in the slip load as a result of dynamic loading. The aluminium-aluminium Huck Lockbolted specimens were subjected to an average of 4.2×10^6 endurance cycles before failure at the same loading configuration. Therefore, it can be considered that aluminium-composite Huck Lockbolted assembly, which had not failed at the higher endurance cycles (of 6.6×10^6) exhibited more encouraging results, however, further verification is required prior to making more conclusive recommendations.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This experimental study was conducted for developing a high strength aluminium-composite frictional grip joint to enable modular construction of rail vehicles. The experimental results suggest that the bearing damage of aluminium-composite specimens (without inserts) is initiated at a lower tensile load (less than 50% of ultimate failure load). This reduces the slip load by 20% compared to the existing aluminium-aluminium joints, yet the ultimate failure load showed a less significant reduction of 3.6%. Consequently, a novel big head insert was developed to help resist bearing failure initiation around the hole within the composite plate. The aluminium-composite specimens, which were tested with the big head inserts, showed that the visible bearing damage started at 60kN (12% less than the ultimate failure load) and the ultimate failure load increased by 2.6% (68.2kN) compared

to the existing aluminium-aluminium Huck Lockbolted joint (66.5kN). It is concluded that, the novel big head insert design was able to distribute the compressive load applied by the frictional grip joint over a larger surface area and this contributed to the increase in the load bearing capacity in the composite portion of the joint. As a result of lowering the tendency for bearing failure, the joints with the big head inserts showed a higher slip load compared to the aluminium-composite specimens without inserts (a 9.2% increase). Furthermore, this phenomenon aided an increase in the ultimate failure load of 6.4%. The specimens with big head inserts, which were tested under dynamic loading, showed good fatigue performance compare to the existing aluminium-aluminium joint testing data. The subsequent residual strength testing results showed a reduction in the slip load of 20% after 6.6×10^6 cycles. The concept of designing an aluminium-composite frictional grip joint with a big head insert that performs similarly to the existing aluminium-aluminium Huck Lockbolted joint has been demonstrated. As a future study, it is required to develop the complete S-N curve for the aluminium-composite joint and optimise the insert design.

REFERENCES

- [1] Board Traspotation Research, "Track Design Handbook," 20 05 2012. [Online]. Available: http://onlinepubs.trb.org/onlinepubs/tcrp/tcrp_rpt_155.pdf. [Accessed 02 01 20].
- [2] D. Milovich, "Quora," 02 07 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.quora.com/How-much-lighter-is-carbon-fiber-than-steel-and-aluminium>. [Accessed 06 01 2015].
- [3] A. P. Partnership, Technology Review -Composite Materials for Rail Vehicles, Nottingham: Internal Document, 2014.
- [4] B. T. Mick Roe, *Previous Composite Applications for Rail Vehicle Constrction*, Nottingham: ACIS Project Progress Review, 2014.
- [5] U. o. Newcastle, "New Rail," 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ncl.ac.uk/newrail/research/projects/>. [Accessed 21 10 2014].
- [6] Wilson M. and Ricketts B., *Validation Simulation of New Railway Rolling Stock Using the Finite Element Method*[Online]. Available: <https://www.dynamore.de/en/downloads/papers/03-conference/crash-automotive-applications/validation-simulation-of-new-railway-rolling-stock>. [Accessed 02 01 20].